

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE BIRD MODEL IN ASSESSING SOLAR RADIATION POTENTIAL IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article discusses methods for calculating solar radiation based on the Bird model. The Bird model is one of the relatively simple and reliable methods that enables accurate calculation of solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface. The article analyzes the parameters of the model and the factors affecting them to accurately calculate solar radiation. Additionally, the application of the Bird model in Uzbekistan and its potential for efficient utilization of solar energy are discussed. The Bird model provides accurate results by considering various atmospheric factors and the angle of the sun relative to the Earth when calculating solar radiation. Due to its simplicity and accuracy, this model is widely used in solar energy, climatology, and atmospheric research. The article examines the technical aspects, applications, and limitations of the Bird model, along with its advantages over other models. Thanks to its effectiveness under clear sky conditions, the Bird model is widely utilized in evaluating the efficiency of solar energy systems.*

Keywords: *bird model, solar radiation, GHI, DNI, DHI, air mass, atmospheric optics.*

Introduction: Solar energy is one of the renewable energy sources that can play a leading role in Uzbekistan's future energy portfolio. Accurate modeling of solar radiation is of great importance in various fields, including solar energy, meteorology, and environmental monitoring. Knowing the amount of solar radiation reaching the Earth is crucial for improving the efficiency of energy systems, optimizing building designs, and studying climate change. Various models are used to calculate solar radiation, and the Bird model is one of them. The Bird model allows for determining the amount of solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface by accounting for absorption, scattering, and obstruction of solar radiation in the atmosphere. To calculate solar radiation and its distribution, many other models used in solar energy can be cited as examples. These include the Liu-Jordan model, Perez model, ASHRAE model, Iqbal model, Hay and Davies model, Klein model, Klucher model, Duffie and Beckman model, Hottel model, Gueymard model, Erbs model, REST2 model, Solis model, and others. These models are utilized for calculating and optimizing different aspects of solar radiation.

Analysis of Existing Models.

Liu-Jordan Model: Diffuse Radiation: This model is designed for analyzing diffuse radiation and considers only an isotropic sky. This means that diffuse radiation is assumed to be uniform in all directions of the sky. By accepting the isotropic nature of diffuse radiation, the Liu-Jordan model provides a simple yet useful approach for solar collectors [1],[16].

Perez Model: More Accurate Analysis: The Perez model analyzes the diffuse component of solar radiation anisotropically and considers various sky conditions, including cloudy or partly cloudy skies. **Broader Scope:** It is highly effective in analyzing the intensity of solar radiation under different meteorological conditions and is widely used in solar energy applications [6],[17].

ASHRAE Model: Solar Heat: This model focuses primarily on measuring the thermal effects of solar radiation and is mainly used in processes related to thermal energy generation. **Standardized Approach:** The ASHRAE (American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers) model is a standard tool, particularly for evaluating the thermal efficiency of solar collectors [3].

Clear Sky Model: This model only considers clear sky conditions and calculates the distribution of solar radiation in such environments. It is primarily used for analyzing maximum levels of solar radiation.

Iqbal Model: Isotropic Diffusion: This model assumes isotropic diffusion of diffuse radiation and calculates solar radiation metrics for simple surfaces. **Climatic Conditions:** The Iqbal model typically provides accuracy by taking into account climatic conditions and the optical thickness of the sky [4].

REST2 (Radiative Energy in the Solar Spectrum for Terrestrial Environments) Model: This model is used for calculating the spectral distribution of solar radiation and accounts for various components of light passing through the atmosphere, including aerosol concentration, turbidity (optical thickness of air), water vapor, and ozone levels [17].

These models enable more precise and comprehensive measurement of solar radiation distribution and are applied to efficiently collect and utilize solar energy. Each model is valuable for specific conditions and purposes.

Methodology

The Bird model, developed in 1981 by Richard Bird and his colleagues, allows for the accurate calculation of solar radiation using various parameters. These parameters depend on factors such as solar altitude, atmospheric conditions (aerosols, ozone, water vapor, etc.), and air mass. The Bird model calculates three main types of solar radiation:

- Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI),
- Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI),
- Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI).

The Bird model was designed to provide precise predictions of solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface. It uses an accurate and comprehensive method for solar radiation calculations, considering several physical factors, including:

Atmospheric Optical Thickness: Solar rays passing through the atmosphere are attenuated or scattered by dust, water vapor, and other particles. The Bird model incorporates this process using the concept of optical thickness, which helps measure the transparency of the atmosphere.

Impact of Aerosols and Dust: Dust and aerosols in the atmosphere scatter solar radiation, reducing direct radiation while increasing diffuse radiation. The Bird model accounts for these effects to provide accurate solar energy forecasts.

Ozone Layer: The ozone layer absorbs ultraviolet (UV) rays from the sun. By considering the thickness of the ozone layer, the Bird model delivers a more accurate assessment of the solar radiation spectrum.

Solar Zenith Angle: The position of the sun in the sky (zenith angle) determines the intensity of solar radiation. The Bird model calculates this angle to estimate the amount of solar energy.

Clear Sky Conditions: The model is primarily designed for clear sky conditions, meaning clouds are not considered, making the Bird model suitable for clear-sky locations.

Differences Between the Bird Model and Other Models: Various models for solar radiation calculation differ in how they account for atmospheric parameters, their suitability for specific conditions, and their levels of accuracy. Compared to other widely used models, the Bird model has the following advantages and distinctions:

1. Perez model. Application: Designed for both cloudy and clear conditions, this model accounts for various atmospheric states, including cloud cover, providing higher accuracy in diverse climates. **Accuracy:** The Perez model achieves accuracy up to $\pm 5\%$, making it more precise than the Bird model, especially under variable atmospheric conditions [17]. **Usage:** Commonly employed for optimizing photovoltaic systems and efficient solar energy utilization.

2. Liu-Jordan model. Application: This model is used for calculating diffuse radiation and for inclined surfaces but assumes an isotropic sky, meaning it may not accurately represent real weather conditions. **Accuracy:** As a simpler model, it has relatively high error margins, with errors ranging between 15-20% in some cases [16]. **Usage:** Primarily used in the design of buildings and solar thermal systems.

3. REST2 model. Application: The REST2 model provides better consideration of aerosol concentration and turbidity levels in the atmosphere, making it more complex than the Bird model. It is well-suited for precise climatic conditions. **Accuracy:** REST2 offers greater precision than the Bird model, with error margins reduced to $\pm 3-4\%$ [17]. **Usage:** Widely applied in scientific research and solar radiation forecasting.

Differences in Values: The difference in results between the Perez and Bird models can range between 5-10%, particularly in cloudy conditions. The REST2 model is more precise than the Bird model, with discrepancies of 3-6% observed under various climate conditions [17]. These figures provide a clearer understanding of the suitability and accuracy of each model for specific applications.

Calculation Methodology

In the past, solar radiation was calculated using the Bird model through the following main equations:

Direct Solar Radiation on a Horizontal Surface (W/m^2):

$$I_d = I_0 \cos(\theta_z) (0,9662) \cdot \tau_r \cdot \tau_0 \cdot \tau_\omega \cdot \tau_a \cdot \tau_{UM} \quad (1)$$

Solar Radiation from Atmospheric Scattering on a Horizontal Surface (W/m^2):

$$I_{as} = I_0 \cos(\theta_z) (0,79) \cdot \tau_0 \cdot \tau_\omega \cdot \tau_a \cdot \tau_{AA} \quad (2)$$

Total Solar Radiation on a Horizontal Surface (W/m^2):

$$I_T = \frac{(I_d + I_{as})}{(1 - r_g r_s)} \quad (3)$$

Rayleigh Scattering Transmission Coefficient:

$$\tau_r = \exp[-0,0903(M')^{0,84} \cdot (1 + M' - (M')^{1,01})] \quad (4)$$

Ozone Absorption Transmission Coefficient:

$$\tau_0 = 1 - 0,1611X_0 \cdot (1 + 139,48X_0)^{-0,3035} - 0,002715X_0 \cdot (1 + 0,44X_0 + 0,0003X_0^2)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

Total Ozone in an Inclined Path (cm):

$$X_0 = U_0 \cdot m \quad (6)$$

Mixed Gas Absorption Transmission (CO_2 and O_2):

$$\tau_{UM} = \exp[-0,0127(M')^{0,26}] \quad (7)$$

Water Vapor Absorption Transmission Coefficient:

$$\tau_\omega = 1 - 2,4959X_\omega \cdot [(1 + 79,034X_\omega)^{0,6828} + 6,385X_\omega]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

Total Water Content Along the Path:

$$X_{\omega} = U_{\omega} \cdot m \quad (9)$$

Aerosol Absorption Transmission Coefficient:

$$\tau_{AA} = 1 - K_1(1 - m + m^{1,06})(1 - \tau_a) \quad (10)$$

Air Mass Calculation:

$$m = [\cos \theta_z + 0,15(93,885 - \theta_z)^{-1,25}]^{-1} \quad (11)$$

Modern calculations often differ from older methods. The Bird model is now expressed through the following equation: Updated Standard Equation for Bird Model:

$$I = I_0 \cdot \tau_r \cdot \tau_0 \cdot \tau_{\omega} \cdot \tau_a \cdot \tau_g \quad (12)$$

Each coefficient represents the effect of various gases and particles in the atmosphere on solar radiation. This formula, introduced by Richard Bird and Robert Hulstrom in 1981, is a standard for the Bird model. I — Solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface (W/m²), I_0 — Extraterrestrial solar radiation, τ_r — (Rayleigh scattering), τ_0 — Ozone absorption, τ_{ω} — Water vapor absorption, τ_a — Aerosol scattering and absorption, τ_g — General gas absorption.

These parameters are the main coefficients of the Bird model, which allow for an accurate calculation of how solar radiation is scattered, absorbed, and reaches the Earth's surface through the atmosphere [2]. Below, they are explained in detail:

Rayleigh scattering takes into account the scattering of solar rays by atmospheric molecules. This coefficient represents the interaction of solar radiation with molecules in the atmosphere and is expressed by the following equation:

$$\tau_r = \exp(-0,008735 \cdot (1 + 0,0006 \cdot P) \cdot (\frac{m}{1+0,0044 \cdot m})) \quad (13)$$

P – Atmospheric pressure (mbar), m — Optical air mass.

Solar radiation is absorbed in the ozone layer. The absorption level depends on the thickness of the ozone and is calculated using the following equation:

$$\tau_0 = \exp(-K_0 \cdot X_0 \cdot m) \quad (14)$$

K_0 – Ozone absorption coefficient, X_0 – Ozone thickness (Dobson).

Water vapor in the atmosphere also absorbs solar radiation. This absorption is determined by the following equation:

$$\tau_{\omega} = \exp(-0,2385 \cdot K_{\omega} \cdot X_{\omega} \cdot m) \quad (13)$$

K_{ω} – absorption coefficient of water vapor, X_{ω} – amount of water vapor (expressed in cm).

Aerosols in the atmosphere absorb and scatter solar radiation. The absorption by aerosols is represented by the following formula:

$$\tau_a = \exp(-A \cdot m^B) \quad (14)$$

A and B – empirical coefficients for aerosol optical depth.

Optical air mass: The optical air mass measures the path length of solar radiation through the atmosphere and is calculated using the following formula:

$$m = \frac{1}{\cos \theta_z + 0,50572 \cdot (96,07995 - \theta_z)^{-1,6364}} \quad (15)$$

According to the Bird model, DNI (direct normal irradiance) is expressed using the following equations:

$$DNI = I_0 \cos(\theta_z) \cdot \tau_r \cdot \tau_0 \cdot \tau_{\omega} \cdot \tau_a \cdot \tau_g \quad (16)$$

$$I_b = I_0 \cdot e^{-(\tau_r + \tau_0 + \tau_{\omega} + \tau_a + \tau_g) \cdot m} \quad (17)$$

These formulas are used to calculate the direct transmission of solar radiation through the atmosphere. The primary factors considered here include the solar zenith angle, ozone amount,

water vapor, and aerosol absorption. Here: I_0 – extraterrestrial solar irradiance (solar radiation above the atmosphere), θ_z – solar zenith angle, calculated using the following formula:

$$\theta_z = \arccos(\sin(\varphi) \cdot \sin(\delta) + \cos(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\delta) \cdot \cos(\omega)) \quad (18)$$

Here: φ – latitude of the observation point, δ – solar declination, which can also be found in international data sources, ω – hour angle, calculated based on time.

Extraterrestrial solar radiation: Solar radiation outside the atmosphere varies depending on the distance between the Earth and the Sun. This value is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_0 = I_s \left(1 + 0,033 \cdot \cos\left(\frac{360}{365} \cdot N\right)\right) \quad (19)$$

I_s – Solar constant ($\sim 1367 \text{ W/m}^2$), N – Day of the year (1-365).

Diffuse Solar Radiation. Diffuse radiation reaches the Earth's surface even under clear-sky conditions due to scattering by atmospheric molecules and aerosols. The diffuse component can be calculated using the following formula:

$$I_d = I_0 \cdot (0.271 - 0.294) \cdot e^{-(\tau_r + \tau_o + \tau_\omega + \tau_a + \tau_g) \cdot m} \quad (20)$$

Global Solar Radiation. Global radiation is the total amount of solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface, including both direct and diffuse components. It can be expressed as:

$$I_g = I_b \cdot \cos \theta_z + I_d \quad (21)$$

Where I_g is the global radiation (W/m^2).

Application of the Bird Model in Uzbekistan: Uzbekistan has exceptionally high solar radiation levels. For instance, in the southern regions of the country, the annual solar radiation reaches 2100 kW/m^2 , which is twice as high as in Central Europe [1]. By applying the Bird model, it is possible to efficiently utilize solar energy in these regions. As a small experiment, we will calculate solar radiation using the Bird model based on data from the Parkent meteorological station in Tashkent. The following parameters were adopted for this purpose:

Ozone layer: 0.3 atm.cm,

Water vapor amount: 1.42 cm,

Aerosol optical depth: 0.27.

Under these conditions, the Bird model was used to compute direct (DNI), diffuse (DHI), and global (GHI) solar radiation indices.

Conclusion

Accurate calculation of solar radiation using the Bird model expands opportunities for utilizing solar energy in Uzbekistan. This model provides essential data for designing solar power plants and improving their efficiency. Given the high levels of solar radiation across Uzbekistan, calculations based on the Bird model are of great significance.

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